

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.

Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	65	-15.40	CCCAGCTGCCACCAGC-CTACACC TGGTC--TCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.2E-2
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	713	-25.40	TCCAGACCCTGTGGCCCTGCACC TGGTCT-CTACG-TCGTGACGTGG	2.93E-1
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2066	-18.50	GCCAGAGCAT-CATCGC-CTACACC : TGGTCTC-TACGT--CGTGACGTGG	1.23E-1
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2261	-20.90	TGCAGTACGGCAGCTTCTGCACC TGGTCTCTACGTGCG-TGACGTGG	2.04E-1
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	3691	-21.00	ACCA-TCATGCTGTGTGCATG : TGGTCTCTACGTGCTGACGTGG	3.8E-2
hsa_mir_143	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	3798	-16.80	GGGCGTGAAGCTGCACTACACC TGGTCTCTACGTGCTGACGTGG	2.15E-2
let_7a_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1303	-13.50	GCCTGGAACAGC-AACAACCTCG : : : TTGAT-ATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	3.19E-1
let_7a_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1453	-16.30	GGCT--TCAAC-TGCTACTTCC : : : TTGATATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	1.33E-3
let_7a_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2566	-17.40	AACGGCCTGACCGTGTGCCTCC : : TTGATATGTTGG-ATGATGGAGT	2.89E-1
mir_145_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	3437	-19.20	ACAGCTTCAAGGAGGAGCTGGAC : TCCCTAAGGACCCCTTTGACCTG	4.55E-2
mir_15b_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	770	-13.80	GGTGGACAGCAGGCGGCTGCTT : ACATTTG--GTACTACACGACGAT	3.59E-2
mir_15b_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2876	-12.90	TGAACACCCTGGTGAAGCAGCTG : : ACATTTGGTACTAC-ACGACGAT	3.31E-2
mir_15b_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	3701	-14.50	TGTGCTGCATGACAGCTGCTG : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	3.8E-2

